

Supplementary material for: Crystal-size dependence of dipolar ferromagnetic order between Mn₆ Single-Molecule Magnets

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This supporting information contains additional details about: (1) the synthesis of bulk Mn₆, (2) the compressed fluids techniques used to obtain the microcrystals, (3) X-ray crystallography of bulk samples, (4) X-ray crystallography of the crystallites, (5) magnetization measurements, (6) specific heat measurements, (7) the micro-SQUID susceptometer, (8) AC susceptibility measurements obtained with it and (8) the theoretical modelling of a spin lattice with pure dipolar interactions.

1.- SYNTHESIS OF BULK MN₆

The synthesis of the unprocessed bulk material followed the protocol reported in [1], which we briefly outline here. Reaction of Et₂dbmH, a bis-ethyl version of dbmH (dibenzoylmethane), with MnBr₂ yields the five-coordinate, square-pyramidal complex [MnBr(Et₂dbm)₂]. Slow hydrolysis in CH₂Cl₂/MeCN over two weeks gives the final compound [Mn₆O₄Br₄(Et₂dbm)₆] that is used as the starting material for the recrystallization in compressed fluids (see next section 2). Looked under the microscope (Fig. S1a), this material shows the presence of a large distribution of crystal sizes. Its crystal structure was determined by X-ray diffraction as described in section 3. Results of magnetic and heat capacity experiments are shown in Fig. 2 of the main text (see also sections 4 and 5 below). They confirm it has the molecular spin and magnetic anisotropy that were reported previously [1, 2].

2.- RECRYSTALLIZATION WITH COMPRESSED FLUIDS TECHNIQUES

Conventional crystallization is typically driven by temperature or composition changes which propagate slowly and non-homogeneously in the media. This approach provides little control over the size of the resulting par-

ticles. In contrast, the driving agent in compressed fluids techniques is the solvation power tuned by pressure changes which propagate faster and more homogeneously, enabling a greater control over the crystal size. A thorough description of the techniques can be found elsewhere [3]. Here we provide a brief description of the two main techniques employed in this study. Depending on the experimental methodology, we distinguish between Gas Anti-Solvent (GAS) method and the Aerosol Solvent Extraction System (ASES) method. Both techniques commonly use CO₂ as compressed fluid due to its non-inflammable properties.

In the GAS method, used for samples A, B and C, the first step is to introduce a solution containing the diluted Mn₆ inside an autoclave. The solvent used is an acetonitrile/CH₂Cl₂ mixture for samples A and B, whereas an acetone/ethyl acetate mixture is used for sample C. The autoclave is thereafter pressurised with CO₂ ($X_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.9$) under constant temperature. The system is left under mechanical agitation to homogenize the solution for several minutes. Finally, the new microcrystals are filtered and removed from the chamber. The autoclave is supplied with N₂ gas to maintain pressure constant.

The ASES technique has been used to produce the smallest size crystals (Sample D). The CO₂ is continuously introduced ($Q_{\text{CO}_2} = 41$ ml/min) in a high-pressure autoclave. The pressure is kept constant using a back pressure regulator valve. Once temperature and pressure conditions inside the autoclave are in equilibrium, pure solvent is introduced through an atomization nozzle to control the CO₂ concentration for a few minutes. Thereafter, the solution containing the molecular material is also introduced ($Q_{\text{sol}} = 5$ ml/min) in the autoclave where the microparticles crystallize. The solvent is an acetone/ethyl acetate mixture. At the end of the process the autoclave is depressurized to atmospheric pressure and the microcrystals are removed.

Figure S1 shows optical images of the resulting micro-

FIG. S1. Optical images of (a) unprocessed Mn_6 , (b) sample A, (c) sample B and (d) sample C microcrystals.

FIG. S2. Size distribution of the three smallest samples measured by dynamic light scattering.

crystals for samples A, B and C. A SEM image of sample D is shown in the main text.

The size distribution of the different sets of crystallites is measured using a dynamic light scattering technique. Figure S2 shows the results for the three smallest samples.

3.- X-RAY CRYSTALLOGRAPHY OF BULK SAMPLES

The x-ray structure of $[Mn_6O_4Br_4(Et_2dbm)_6]$ has not been previously reported, in part due to poor diffraction systematically observed and likely related to disorder of the ethyl arms. The crystal structure is now de-

termined by using a synchrotron source in block crystals obtained upon concentration of an acetonitrile solution of $MnBr(Et_2dbm)_2$. Data for $[Mn_6O_4Br_4(Et_2dbm)_6]$ were collected at 100 K on a black block with dimensions $0.32 \times 0.30 \times 0.10 \text{ mm}^3$ on a Bruker D8 diffractometer on the Advanced Light Source beam-line 11.3.1 at Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, from a silicon 111 monochromator ($\lambda = 0.7749 \text{ \AA}$). Data reduction and absorption corrections were performed with SAINT and SADABS [4], respectively. The structure was solved and refined by full-matrix least squares on F^2 with respectively SHELXS and SHELXL [5, 6]. There was significant diffraction only up to ca. 1.15 \AA , at which the data were cut. Such poor diffraction was repeatedly observed for crystals of any size tested, even with synchrotron radiation source, indicating the diffraction drop is intrinsic to the available crystals. This poor diffraction is at the origin of the poor reflections to parameters ratio, low θ_{full} and $\sin(\theta_{max})$ values. Several phenyl rings were refined as rigid group and all ethyl groups were highly disordered and refined with 1,2 and 1,3 distance restraints. At the end of the refinement voids remained in the structure containing virtually no electron density peaks. These were analyzed and taken into account with PLATON/SQUEEZE [7]. Only very small electron density was thus recovered indicating the voids do not contain significant amounts of solvent molecules. A significant 2% improvement in $R1$ was obtained, though.

At 100 K, bulk Mn_6 crystallizes in the monoclinic $P2_1/n$ space group and its asymmetric unit coincides with the molecule formula (Table S1), the unit cell containing four such molecules. The six Mn(III) sites form a highly symmetric octahedron core that are connected through μ^3 -oxide and μ^3 -bromide ions forming a pyramid with the four Br ions at the apices and the four oxide O at the center of the faces (Fig. 1a in the main manuscript). The coordination sphere of each Mn site is completed by one chelating β -diketone from one of the Et_2dbm ligands. Each Mn site presents a similar octahedral coordination sphere with a marked Jahn-Teller elongation axis as is typical with Mn^{3+} ions. These axial positions are occupied by bromide ions with Mn-Br bond distances in the range $2.730 - 2.824 \text{ \AA}$, while the equatorial plane is composed of two oxide O, trans to the two β -diketone O, with Mn-O bond length in the range $1.829 - 1.950 \text{ \AA}$ (see Table S2). The Jahn-Teller axes approximately coincide with the edges of a pyramid, thus forming mutual angles that hardly depart from 60° as gauged by the $Br \cdots Br \cdots Br$ angles (all within the $58.5 - 61.4^\circ$). The corresponding Mn-Br-Mn are however in the range $68.65 - 70.91^\circ$ as a result of bent Br-Mn-Br axes, see Table S3). Thus, and as previously argued, the associated magneto-crystalline anisotropy likely almost cancels out over the Mn_6 molecule resulting in a rather isotropic molecule. The Mn_6 molecules arrange in two different orientations in the lattice. Molecules with the

Formula	C ₁₁₄ H ₁₁₄ Br ₄ Mn ₆ O ₁₆
FW (g mol ⁻¹)	2389.33
T (K)	100
Wavelength (Å)	0.7749
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>n</i>
<i>a</i> (Å)	17.749(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	23.321(4)
<i>c</i> (Å)	27.277(4)
α (°)	90
β (°)	92.775(2)
γ (°)	90
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	11277(3)
<i>Z</i>	4
ρ_{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	1.407
μ (mm ⁻¹)	2.643
Independent reflections	7757 (<i>R</i> _{int} =0.0513)
Data/restraints/ parameters	7757/656/1117
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.661
Final <i>R</i> ₁ / <i>wR</i> ₂ [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	0.1253/0.3771
Final <i>R</i> ₁ / <i>wR</i> ₂ [all data]	0.1487/0.4028
largest diff. peak and hole (eÅ ³)	1.649/-1.389

TABLE S1. Crystal data for [Mn₆O₄Br₄(Et₂dbm)₆], Mn₆

same orientation form alternate planes perpendicular to the *c* axis as seen in Fig. 1b of the main manuscript.

There are no significant intermolecular interactions, besides a weak $\pi \cdots \pi$ interaction between two Et₂dbm ligands from two neighboring molecules, giving rise to the shortest inter-molecule separation at 14.214 Å, defined as the Mn₆ core centroid-to-centroid distance.

All details can be found in CCDC 1452338 that contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif. Crystallographic and refinement parameters are summarized in Table S1. Selected bond lengths and angles are given in Table S2 and Table S3.

4.- X-RAY CRYSTALLOGRAPHY OF THE CRYSTALLITES

Multiple unit cell determination on tiny single crystals from sample C (average size 7.5 μm) were performed at the same facility used for the unprocessed sample, giving in all cases monoclinic cells very similar to that of the bulk crystals, although with poorer agreement with the strict monoclinic symmetry. Cell parameters ranged 17.2 – 17.9 Å for *a*, 23.1 – 23.8 Å for *b*, 26.3 – 27.4 Å for *c*, 92.1 – 93.2° for β and 10840 – 11310 Å³ for *V*, corresponding to a maximum deviation of 4% in cell volume with respect to the bulk crystals.

Mn1-O6	1.879(13)	Mn4-O4	1.873(13)
Mn1-O2	1.892(12)	Mn4-O11	1.915(14)
Mn1-O1	1.904(14)	Mn4-O1	1.920(14)
Mn1-O5	1.950(16)	Mn4-O12	1.927(16)
Mn1-Br2	2.792(4)	Mn4-Br2	2.773(4)
Mn1-Br1	2.801(4)	Mn4-Br3	2.810(4)
Mn2-O3	1.829(12)	Mn5-O14	1.849(19)
Mn2-O1	1.863(13)	Mn5-O2	1.890(14)
Mn2-O8	1.933(14)	Mn5-O4	1.895(13)
Mn2-O7	1.943(15)	Mn5-O13	1.948(16)
Mn2-Br3	2.820(4)	Mn5-Br2	2.766(4)
Mn2-Br1	2.824(4)	Mn5-Br4	2.792(4)
Mn3-O2	1.858(13)	Mn6-O4	1.852(12)
Mn3-O3	1.886(14)	Mn6-O15	1.884(16)
Mn3-O9	1.895(18)	Mn6-O3	1.909(13)
Mn3-O10	1.929(15)	Mn6-O16	1.919(14)
Mn3-Br4	2.771(4)	Mn6-Br3	2.730(5)
Mn3-Br1	2.790(4)	Mn6-Br4	2.748(5)
Mn1···Mn3	3.203(4)	Mn2···Mn4	3.213(4)
Mn1···Mn5	3.211(5)	Mn3···Mn5	3.193(4)
Mn1···Mn2	3.217(4)	Mn3···Mn6	3.201(5)
Mn1···Mn4	3.223(5)	Mn4···Mn5	3.154(5)
Mn2···Mn3	3.166(5)	Mn4···Mn6	3.214(4)
Mn2···Mn6	3.185(5)	Mn5···Mn6	3.198(5)

TABLE S2. Selected bond distances (Å) and Mn···Mn separations (Å) in the structure of [Mn₆O₄Br₄(Et₂dbm)₆], Mn₆. Longer bonds corresponding to the Mn³⁺ Jahn-Teller elongated axes are highlighted in bold.

Mn2-O1-Mn1	117.3(7)	Mn3-Br1-Mn1	69.89(10)
Mn2-O1-Mn4	116.3(7)	Mn3-Br1-Mn2	68.65(11)
Mn1-O1-Mn4	114.9(7)	Mn1-Br1-Mn2	69.77(10)
Mn3-O2-Mn5	116.8(6)	Mn5-Br2-Mn4	69.43(12)
Mn3-O2-Mn1	117.3(7)	Mn5-Br2-Mn1	70.59(11)
Mn5-O2-Mn1	116.2(6)	Mn4-Br2-Mn1	70.80(11)
Mn2-O3-Mn3	116.9(7)	Mn6-Br3-Mn4	70.91(11)
Mn2-O3-Mn6	116.9(7)	Mn6-Br3-Mn2	70.02(12)
Mn3-O3-Mn6	115.0(7)	Mn4-Br3-Mn2	69.60(11)
Mn6-O4-Mn4	119.3(7)	Mn6-Br4-Mn3	70.88(12)
Mn6-O4-Mn5	117.2(7)	Mn6-Br4-Mn5	70.51(12)
Mn4-O4-Mn5	113.6(6)	Mn3-Br4-Mn5	70.04(11)
Br1···Br2···Br3	60.7(2)	Br2···Br1···Br3	59.7(2)
Br1···Br2···Br4	59.9(2)	Br2···Br1···Br4	59.8(2)
Br1···Br3···Br2	59.7(2)	Br2···Br3···Br4	60.3(2)
Br1···Br3···Br4	60.0(2)	Br2···Br4···Br3	60.7(2)
Br1···Br4···Br2	60.3(2)	Br3···Br1···Br4	58.6(2)
Br1···Br4···Br3	61.4(2)	Br3···Br2···Br4	59.0(2)
Br2-Mn1-Br1	166.77(14)	Br2-Mn4-Br3	166.93(15)
Br3-Mn2-Br1	167.13(14)	Br2-Mn5-Br4	167.53(16)
Br4-Mn3-Br1	168.30(15)	Br3-Mn6-Br4	168.00(16)

TABLE S3. Selected angles (Å) in the structure of [Mn₆O₄Br₄(Et₂dbm)₆], Mn₆.

FIG. S3. Magnetization of samples C and D measured as a function of magnetic field at different temperatures. The good scaling of all curves when plotted as a function of B/T supports the application of the paramagnetic Brillouin model, Eq. (S1), to extract from these data the molecular spin $S = 12$ and $g = 1.95$ factor.

5.- MAGNETIZATION

The magnetization of Mn_6 clusters measured above 2 K can be described by a Brillouin model for an isotropic paramagnet.

$$M = gS \left[\frac{2S+1}{2S} \coth\left(\frac{(2S+1)x}{2S}\right) - \frac{1}{2S} \coth\left(\frac{x}{2S}\right) \right] \quad (S1)$$

where x is:

$$x = \frac{gS\mu_B}{k_B} \frac{B}{T}. \quad (S2)$$

where S and g are the molecular spin and Landee factor, respectively, $B = \mu_0H$ is the externally applied magnetic

field and T is the temperature. This simple approximation holds at sufficiently high temperatures compared to both T_c and the magnetic anisotropy, and allows the determination of g and S . The solid line in Fig. 2c of the main text is a fit based on Eq.(S1) with $S = 12$ and $g = 1.95$. Figure S3 shows additional magnetization curves measured on samples C and D as a function of magnetic field at different temperatures, which show the scaling in B/T that Eq. (S1) predicts.

6.-SPECIFIC HEAT

The specific heat of a crystal of molecular nanomagnets can be divided in two contributions: one associated with lattice and molecular vibrations and another one originating from the magnetic levels of the molecules. The acoustic modes, due to intermolecular vibrations, are described by the Debye model:

$$c_p/R = \left(\frac{T}{\theta_D}\right)^3 \int_0^{\theta_D/T} \frac{x^4 e^x dx}{(e^x - 1)^2} \quad (S3)$$

where R is the universal gas constant and θ_D is the Debye temperature. The dashed line in Fig. 2d of the main manuscript is a fit based on Eq.S3 with $\theta_D \simeq 8$ K. The low value of the Debye temperature is characteristic of molecular crystals, formed by very weakly interacting clusters.

At even lower temperatures, the specific heat is dominated by the Schottky contribution arising from the magnetic levels, which can be calculated by using the fluctuation-dissipation theorem:

$$c_m/R = \frac{\langle U^2 \rangle - \langle U \rangle^2}{T^2} \quad (S4)$$

where U is the magnetic internal energy of the system:

$$U = N_A \frac{\sum_i E_i e^{-\frac{E_i}{k_B T}}}{Z}. \quad (S5)$$

Z is the partition function and E_i are the magnetic energy levels obtained from the diagonalization of the spin Hamiltonian of each molecule:

$$\mathcal{H} = -DS_z^2 - g\mu_B \vec{S} \cdot \vec{B} \quad (S6)$$

where S_z is the spin projection along z and D is the uniaxial anisotropy parameter. The solid line in Fig. 2d of the main manuscript is a fit based on Eq. S4 with $D/k_B = 0.013$ K.

7.-MICRO-SQUID AC SUSCEPTOMETRY

AC magnetic susceptibility measurements were performed with the micro-SQUID susceptometers reported in [8]. Two illustrative microscopy images of the device, hosting samples of Mn_6 microcrystallites, are shown in Fig. S4a and S4b. The susceptometer is defined by two coils, each made of two identical, 'banana-shaped', sections with approximate dimensions $350 \times 600 \mu\text{m}^2$, fabricated by optical lithography on Nb films deposited onto silicon wafers. One of these coils is coupled to the internal oscillator of a lock-in amplifier to generate the oscillatory excitation magnetic field, with frequency ranging from a few mHz to 200 kHz and amplitude below 1 mG. The second coil, whose geometry and dimensions match those of the excitation coil, has a gradiometric design. It is inductively coupled to the excitation coil and to a dc SQUID sensor, whose output voltage is preamplified by an array of 16 readout SQUIDs and finally measured by the lock-in amplifier, which determines its real and imaginary components. The chip is submerged in the ^3He - ^4He mixture inside the mixing chamber of a dilution refrigerator. This ensures an optimal thermal contact over the full temperature range accessible through this system, from 13 mK up to 3 K.

Polycrystalline Mn_6 samples were mixed with apiezon N grease, in order to further improve its thermal contact with the Helium mixture, and then deposited directly onto one of the two sections forming the pick-up coil (see Fig. S4). The response of the sample to the excitation ac field introduces a net magnetic flux into the SQUID, which generates a non-zero output voltage, proportional to the complex magnetic susceptibility. The signal arising from the very small uncompensation of the empty susceptometer was measured previously under the same temperature and frequency conditions, and then subtracted from the experimental data. In order to get absolute values, the voltage data were scaled against susceptibility results measured with a commercial SQUID susceptometer at temperatures $T > 2$ K and frequencies $\omega < 1$ kHz that overlap with those of the micro-SQUID experiments. An example of this calibration procedure is shown in Fig. S4c.

8.-ADDITIONAL MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY MEASUREMENTS

Figures S5 and S6 show χ' and χ'' data measured on samples C and D, respectively. Data for samples A and B are shown in Fig. 2 of the main text.

FIG. S4. Optical microscopy images of the micro-SQUID susceptometer used in the very low- T ac susceptibility experiments hosting a sample of $12 \mu\text{m}$ (sample B, panel a) and $7.5 \mu\text{m}$ (sample C, panel b) Mn_6 crystals. (c) In-phase component of the ac susceptibility of sample D (220 nm crystals) measured with a commercial SQUID magnetometer and with the micro-SQUID susceptometer at 107 Hz . Data measured in the temperature region ($1.7 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 2.34 \text{ K}$) that is accessible to both experimental systems are used to determine the scaling factor needed to calibrate the micro-SQUID data. Inset: Reciprocal susceptibility obtained from these results.

9.-MODELING OF A PURE DIPOLAR SPIN SYSTEM

Dipolar energy calculations

In the following we discuss in more detail the physics behind the drop in T_c with decreasing crystal size. For

FIG. S5. χ' (top) and χ'' (bottom) of sample C (average crystal size $7\mu\text{m}$) measured as a function of temperature at different frequencies $\omega/2\pi$ ranging from 21 mHz to 63 kHz.

this, we use a simple, yet intuitive, model that has the advantage of allowing the simulation of larger spin ensembles (closer to the thermodynamic limit) than the computationally costly Monte-Carlo simulations.

The interaction energy of a system of N spins coupled only via dipolar interactions is given by:

$$E_{dip}(\vec{r}_{ij}) = \sum_{ij} \frac{\vec{\mu}_i \cdot \vec{\mu}_j}{r_{ij}^3} - \frac{3(\vec{\mu}_i \cdot \vec{r}_{ij})(\vec{\mu}_j \cdot \vec{r}_{ij})}{r_{ij}^5} \quad (\text{S7})$$

where r_{ij} is the distance between a pair of spins $i - j$ and $\vec{\mu} = g\mu_B \vec{S}$ is the magnetic moment. The same Hamiltonian is used in the Monte-Carlo simulations.

Calculations were performed on a body centered tetragonal lattice, shown in Fig. S7a, which provides a close approximation to the Mn_6 crystal lattice (see Fig. 1b in the main text). The minimum attainable energy of a ferromagnetic dipolar domain is plotted in Fig. S7b as a function of the number of spins N_z along the magnetization axis z . In these calculations, the width of the domain in x and y dimensions is fixed to $N_x = N_y = 5$

FIG. S6. χ' (top) and χ'' (bottom) of sample D (average crystal size 220 nm) measured as a function of temperature at different frequencies $\omega/2\pi$ ranging from 21 mHz to 63 kHz.

spins. The energy decreases towards the thermodynamic limit [9] ($E = -(4\pi/3)N\mu^2$) as N_z increases. This is mainly a consequence of the reduction of the demagnetizing factor when the sample approaches a needle shape. On the other hand, by increasing the width of the domain (N_x and N_y) for fixed N_z , the energy per spin decreases, reaching a minimum E_{\min} , and thereafter it increases again, as seen in Fig. S7c. This energy minimum is driven by two competing mechanisms. By increasing N_x and N_y , the number of neighbours increases and therefore E decreases and gets closer to the thermodynamic limit. At the same time, the demagnetizing factor increases and therefore the dipolar energy eventually starts to increase.

To sum up, the minimum energy E_{\min} , that is, the closest the system can get to the thermodynamic limit, is a compromise between the number of spins in each ferromagnetic domain and the demagnetizing factor. Larger samples allow the formation of larger and therefore energetically more stable domains. As the Monte Carlo simulations described below show (see also Fig. 4c in the main text), the minimum energy of the largest ferromagnetic domain is directly linked to T_c . The trend of E_{\min} ver-

FIG. S7. (a) Schematic view of the body centered tetragonal spin lattice used for the theoretical calculation of dipolar interactions energies. Ferromagnetic domains with dimensions (in number of lattice points or spins) N_z along the polarization axis and $N_x = N_y$ along the two perpendicular axes are considered. (b) Normalized dipolar energy E of a ferromagnetic body centered tetragonal domain as a function of the length N_z for a fixed width $N_x = N_y = 5$. (c) E as a function of the the width $N_x = N_y$ and different lengths N_z .

sus lattice size qualitatively agrees with the experimental T_c vs d shown in Fig. 4a of the main text. These calculations allow getting information on the ferromagnetic order stability (and thus indirectly about T_c) for much larger lattice sizes than those affordable to Monte Carlo simulations. Still, the computational cost also increases very rapidly with N_z (see Fig. S8), and it eventually becomes prohibitive for domain sizes larger than $N \sim 10^8$ spins.

Monte Carlo simulations

Finally, we expand the information given in the main text on the Monte Carlo simulations performed on the same lattices. The thermal relaxation of the dipolar spin system was simulated using a classical Metropolis-Montecarlo (MC) algorithm. The large number of spins even in small samples makes unaffordable to model a whole crystal. To further simplify the analysis, and as originally done on basis of the structure of the Cl analogue [10], the Mn_6 lattice was approximated to a body-centered tetragonal lattice, shown in Fig. S7a, with $a' = b' = 18.0 \text{ \AA}$ and $c' = 17.7 \text{ \AA}$. The initial conditions are set to a high-temperature randomized set of Ising spins ('up' or 'down') pointing along the z axis. Thereafter the temperature of the simulation is decreased. Figure 4 of the main text shows the normalized E as a function of T simulated for different domain sizes. The width of the magnetic domains is fixed to $N_x = N_y = 5$ spins while the length N_z varies. Each energy point is obtained after 3×10^6 MC steps to ensure the system has reached thermal equilibrium. A step-like decrease of the energy is observed as temperature is decreased. This drop is associated to a transition from a fully disordered paramag-

netic state to a ferromagnetic state at low temperatures. Interestingly, the minimum attainable energy of the ferromagnetic state decreases as N_z is increased. The same size-dependent critical behavior can be observed in the differential specific heat (c_p , see also Fig. 4 in the main text). c_p peaks at a decreasing T_c as the length of the domain is decreased. The minimum energy E_{\min} , that is, the closest the system can be to the thermodynamic limit is a compromise between the number of neighbours and the demagnetizing factor. This minimum energy is in turn directly linked with T_c , thus providing support to te method we used to deal with larger lattices (see previous section). The variation of T_c with lattice size is in agreement with the experimental results.

FIG. S8. a) Domain width (N_x, N_y) for which the dipolar energy is closest to the thermodynamic limit for a specific domain length (N_z). The estimated domain width for a $40\mu\text{m}$ -long magnetic domain is expected to be in the range $N_x = N_y = 40 - 45$ (red ellipsoid). b) Number of operations (sums) required to calculate the dipolar energy of a given magnetic size. The empty dots signal the domain width that gives dipolar energy closest to the thermodynamic limit for each N_z . These values are extrapolated to a possible range of values for the largest domains.

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